

Polarographic Study of Zinc(II)—L-Tryptophan System vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Process

J. C. KHATRI and MUKHTAR SINGH*

Chemical Laboratories, Agra College, Agra-282 002

Manuscript received 28 February 1979, revised 26 June 1986, accepted 12 August 1986

IN continuation of earlier publication¹, we now report the results of our studies on the composition and stability constants of Zn²⁺—L-tryptophan complexes.

Experimental

Solutions of ZnCl₂ and NaClO₄ were prepared from reagent grade chemicals in conductivity water by standard analytical procedures. L-Tryptophan was (Reanal, A.R.) used as a ligand. The concentration of Zn²⁺ in each case was kept at 1 × 10⁻³ M.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL-50 polyflex galvanometer was used. All the measurements were made at 25 ± 0.1°. Purified nitrogen gas was passed through the solution to deaerate it. Saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaClO₄, open circuit): *m* = 2.46 mg s⁻¹, *t* = 2.44 s; *m*^{2/3} *t*^{1/6} = 2.11 mg^{2/3} s^{1/6}, *h*_{0.01} = 61.8 cm. The number of electrons (*n*) involved in the reduction process was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon², and gave the value of *n* = 2 at pH 7.

Results and Discussion

Polarograms of the solutions containing 1 × 10⁻³ M of Zn²⁺ and 1 × 10⁻³ M of L-tryptophan were taken at different pH values. It was observed that shift in *E*_{1/2} was maximum at pH 7, and hence this value was chosen for studying the complex formation. The tryptophan concentration was varied from 0 to 0.10 M. A well defined diffusion-controlled, quasi-reversible³⁻⁵ wave appeared in the absence of L-tryptophan, but in the presence of increasing concentrations of L-tryptophan two waves appeared. For the first wave the plots of *i*_a vs √*h* were found to be linear passing through the origin, while in the case of the second wave the plots were found to be straight lines parallel to *h*-axis, thereby showing that the first wave is diffusion-controlled whereas the second one is kinetically controlled. For the first wave, the plots of log *i*/(*i*_a - *i*) vs *E*_{a,0} were found to be linear with the slope value of the order of ± 86 mV. On applying various criteria⁶⁻⁹ of irreversibility it has been ascertained that the reduction of Zn²⁺—

L-tryptophan complexes at d.m.e. is totally irreversible.

The L-tryptophanate (LT) ion concentration has been calculated¹⁰⁻¹⁶ from the pH of the solution and the p*K* values of L-tryptophan (p*K*₁ = 2.28 and p*K*₂ = 9.72).

TABLE 1—VALUES OF KINETIC PARAMETERS (*αn*_a AND *k*⁰_{*f,h*}) FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTION OF Zn²⁺—L-TRYPTOPHAN SYSTEM

[Zn²⁺] = 1 × 10⁻³ M, [NaClO₄] = 0.1 M, *μ* = 0.10 M, pH = 7, Temp. = 25 ± 0.1°

[L-Tryptophan] × 10 ³ M	<i>i</i> _a μA	- <i>E</i> _{1/2} (S.C.E.)	Slope mV	D × 10 ⁶ cm ² s ⁻¹	<i>αn</i>	<i>k</i> ⁰ _{<i>f,h</i>} cm s ⁻¹
0	7.04	1.07	48	5.50	—	—
10	5.10	1.21	87	4.72	0.61	5.26 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
20	4.22	1.22	85	3.23	0.59	3.73 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
30	3.96	1.23	82	2.84	0.54	2.40 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
40	3.70	1.23	89	2.47	0.50	1.03 × 10 ⁻¹¹
50	2.64	1.24	82	1.26	0.44	2.50 × 10 ⁻¹³

The reversible half-wave potential (*E*_{1/2}^r) has been calculated by Gellings' method¹⁷. A plot of *E*_{1/2}^r vs log [L-Tryptophanate] is a smooth curve showing the formation of successive complexes. The method of DeFord and Hume¹⁸ has been applied to determine the composition and stability constants of the complexes. Two complex species, viz. [Zn(LT)]⁺ and [Zn(LT)₂], with stability constants, log β₁ = 9 and log β₂ = 14.78, are formed. The kinetic parameters (*αn*_a and *k*⁰_{*f,h*}) of the irreversible electrode reaction of Zn²⁺—L-tryptophan system have been calculated by Koutecky's method^{19,20} and are listed in Table 1. A perusal of the data shows that both *αn*_a and *k*⁰_{*f,h*} tend to decrease with increasing concentrations of L-tryptophan. From this it follows²¹ that the electrode reaction of Zn²⁺—L-tryptophan system is rendered increasingly more irreversible with the increase in the concentration of L-tryptophan.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Principal, Agra College, Agra, for facilities.

References

1. J. C. KHATRI, M. SINGH and S. K. JHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 564.
2. T. DEVRIES and J. L. KROON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 2484.
3. P. DELAHAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1430.
4. H. MATSUDA and Y. AYABE, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1959, 63, 1164.
5. J. KORYTA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1972, 6, 67.
6. L. MEITES, "Polarographic Techniques", Interscience, New York, 1965, p. 232.
7. R. GOTO and I. TACHI, *Proc. Int. Polarogr. Congr. Prague*, 1951, 1, 69.
8. P. DELAHAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4944.
9. P. KIVALO, K. B. OLDHAM and H. A. LAITINEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4148.
10. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 2904.

11. R. C. KAPFOR and J. KISHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 350.
12. R. SUNDARESAN and A. K. SUNDARAM, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1974, 79, 161.
13. J. RANGRAJAN, B. I. NEMADE and R. SUNDARESAN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1977, 85, 454.
14. R. SUNDARESAN and A. K. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1971, 9, 148.
15. R. SUNDARESAN, S. C. SARAIYA, T. R. RADHAKRISHNAN and A. K. SUNDARAM, *Electrochim Acta*, 1968, 13, 443.
16. J. RANGRAJAN, R. SUNDARESAN and B. I. NEMADE, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci., Sect. A*, 1977, 86, 327; 1977, 86, 333.
17. P. J. GELLINGS, *Z. Elektrochem. Ber. Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1962, 66, 477, 481, 799; 1963, 67, 167.
18. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5321.
19. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, 47, 323; *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1953, 18, 597.
20. J. KOUTECKY and J. CIZEK, *Collect. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1956, 21, 836.
21. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 742.

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of some Primary Alcohols by *N*-Bromobenzamide

V. K. SEERIYAA, V. R. CHOUREY, R. S. VARMAA,
S. K. SOLANKEE and VI. RAA. SHAASTRY*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikrama University,
Ujjeina-456 010

Manuscript received 24 December 1985, accepted
12 August 1986

REPORTS are available in literature on the mechanism of oxidation by chloramine-T¹, chloramine-B², *N*-bromosuccinimide³ and other haloamides, however, no information is available about the modes of the redox reactions of *N*-bromobenzamide (NBB). The different mechanistic pathways reported for the structurally related *N*-haloamides⁴⁻⁷ prompted us to undertake this investigation.

Experimental

Alcohols (B.D.H., A.R. and S.M., G.R.) were purified by the reported method⁸. Acetic acid was distilled over chromic acid before use. Perchloric acid was used as a source of hydrogen ions. All other chemicals used were of B.D.H., A.R. or S.M., G.R. quality. The reaction vessels were coated with black paint to exclude any photochemical effect.

Kinetic measurements: The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess of alcohol over NBB. The temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The solvent used was 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid—water, unless mentioned otherwise. The reactions were followed iodometrically for over 70% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants (K_1) were computed from the plot of $\log [NBB]$ against time. Dupli-

cate kinetic runs indicate that the reaction rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 4.0\%$. Preliminary experiments showed that the reaction is not sensitive to ionic strength hence no attempt was made to keep it constant.

Results

When the alcohol is in excess, the first order plots show that the reaction is composed of two successive steps; the initial slow reaction followed by a fast reaction. Such observations were made in the oxidation of alcohols by *N*-bromosuccinimide⁴⁻⁶. The second faster reaction is attributed to either the oxidation of alcohols by bromine or to the reaction of bromine with carbonyl product⁴. This was suppressed by the addition of 0.005 *M* mercuric acetate.

Dependence of rate on oxidant concentration: The time order of the reaction is found to be one with respect to oxidant as evidenced by the constancy of the first order rate constants at different times. Concentration order of the reaction with respect to oxidant is also one, as evidenced by the independency of the rate constant on the initial concentration of the oxidant. Results obtained are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

[Substrate] = 1.0 mol dm⁻³, [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
[HOAc] = 50% (v/v), [HClO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, Temp. = 323 K

Sl. no.	[NBB] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	$k_1 \times 10^3$, min ⁻¹	
		Ethanol	Propan-1-ol
1.	2.50	1.52	2.78
2.	3.75	1.58	2.82
3.	5.00	1.68	2.80
4.	6.25	1.70	2.78
5.	7.50	1.62	2.76
6.	8.75	1.58	2.84

Dependence of rate on substrate concentration: The rate constants at different initial concentrations of the substrate have been obtained. The plots of pseudo-first order rate constants against substrate concentration exhibit linearity for the given range of substrate concentrations. The plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [C]$ gives a slope value of unity. This

TABLE 2

[NBB] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³,
HOAc = 50% (v/v), [Hg(OAc)₂] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³,
Temp. 323 K

Sl. no.	[Substrate] mol dm ⁻³	$k_1 \times 10^3$	
		Ethanol	Propan-1-ol
1.	0.50	0.82	1.41
2.	0.75	1.21	2.06
3.	1.00	1.68	2.80
4.	1.25	2.02	3.48
5.	1.50	2.40	4.21
6.	2.00	3.20	5.59